

Bridging Local Knowledge and Remote Sensing in Southeast Angola: The Power of Participatory Mapping in Understudied Landscapes

Abstract

Remote sensing-based vegetation mapping approaches play a crucial role in guiding conservation efforts. However, these methods often rely on large-scale data which can lead to overlooking fine-scale environmental and socio-ecological dynamics, potentially undermining local livelihoods. This work explores the classification of vegetation based on local perceptions in the highlands of southeast Angola, emphasizing the limitations of remote-sensing-only based methods for mapping lived landscapes. This region, one of the most remote and isolated of Angola, harbors some of Africa’s best-preserved woodlands and plays a vital role in sustaining southern Africa’s water systems. The region is an ideal candidate for conservation interventions but, we argue here, local livelihoods must play a central role in shaping these strategies. This study employs a mixed-methods approach, conducting remote sensing analyses, participatory mapping, transect walks, and surveys in five rural villages in southeast Angola to incorporate local knowledge into maps. Our findings reveal that locals possess detailed ecological knowledge, identifying five woodland types and two grassland types based on tree density, species composition, fire regimes, and resource use. Vegetation types are multi-functional, meeting diverse subsistence needs. Integrating remote sensing data with participatory methods fosters a holistic understanding of the landscape and highlighting vegetation uses supports local land rights and promotes inclusive, people-centered conservation strategies.

Keywords: Participatory mapping, socio-ecological systems, remote sensing, conservation, woodlands

1. Introduction

Mapping and classifying landscapes using remote sensing tools is instrumental for the management of ecosystems, the monitoring of forests and the conservation of habitats (David et al., 2022). Satellite technologies have made data available at spatial and temporal resolutions that are logistically challenging with conventional, ground-based survey methods alone (Pritchard et al., 2021). However, relying solely on large-scale, remotely-sensed data products and non-contextualized methods can undermine local landscape perspectives, risking inequitable and ineffective natural resource governance.

The sole use of satellite data for land classification can result in simplified territories that lack local meaning (Bennett et al., 2022; Monmonier, 1996; Robbins and Maddock, 2000). Externally defined classifications often dictate how landscapes are evaluated and managed (Latour, 1987), potentially leading to managing ecosystems to fit imposed categories (Veregin, 1995; Robbins & Maddock, 2000). This in turn can influence land interventions in ways that reinforce existing disparities in the distribution of land-derived benefits (Meyfroidt et al., 2022).

Moreover, land classification systems often overlook the distinction between land cover (referring to the physical characteristics of the land) and land use (referring to human activities and management) (Meyer & Turner, 1996), possibly oversimplifying landscape dynamics. Fixed land classifications often emphasize potential uses, especially for activities like crop cultivation and timber extraction, often prioritizing land uses that are more readily mapped (Malavasi, 2020). However, these mapped uses may overlook subsistence and market-oriented uses such as food collection, grazing, medicinal plant harvesting, extraction of non-timber forest products, livestock production, and trade of wild foods and medicinal plants (Robbins & Maddock, 2000).

Different disciplines prioritize distinct land characteristics, leading to diverse interpretations of land data. In ecology, remote sensing classifications typically rely on vegetation structure and composition (Schulz et al., 2019; Wells et al., 2025), whilst for conservation purposes, satellite data frequently assesses biophysical features such as forest cover, forest change, and ecosystem fragmentation (Hernando et al., 2017; Blackman, 2013; Corbane et al., 2015). As a result, the values assigned to the land by conventional ecological and conservation approaches can create tensions between conservation priorities and livelihood needs.

For land interventions (such as management or conservation) to be equitable, it is essential to consider how land classifications are developed, who produces them, the interests shaping their creation, and their impacts on local livelihoods. At the local scale, cultures with strong connections to their land often possess systems for classifying habitats, ecosystems, and landscapes based on local ecological knowledge and their associated uses and values (Berkes et al., 1998; Duvall, 2008; Levinson, 2008; Shepard et al., 2001). Such knowledge often enables communities to manage the land in ways that are compatible with biodiversity

81 conservation (Schulz et al., 2019; Tengö et al., 2014; Garnett et al., 2018). Incorporating local
82 perspectives into remotely-based land classifications can therefore enhance the effectiveness
83 and local acceptance of different types of interventions (Chapin et al., 2005). This approach
84 may not only improve local relevance but also aligns with global initiatives, such as the Post-
85 2020 Global Biodiversity Framework, that recognize the interdependent relationship of local
86 communities with nature (Friedman et al., 2022).

87

88 Mapping processes that attempt to capture local landscape perceptions and knowledge have
89 been developed as a counterapproach to conventional land classification systems.

90 Participatory mapping is a practice that recognizes that conventional maps have historically
91 marginalized alternative views of the world and in response, attempts to give voice to those
92 views through the production of new maps based on local knowledge (Brown and Kyttä,
93 2014; Young and Gilmore, 2017; Dunn, 2007). This practice recognizes that local
94 communities possess detailed knowledge of their land, which can be effectively represented
95 geographically. Participatory maps often include information omitted from conventional
96 maps such as customary land boundaries, traditional resource use, management practices,
97 sacred areas, and historical knowledge, among other locally relevant information (Corbett,
98 2009).

99 By combining insights from participatory maps with remote sensing methods, a richer
100 understanding of landscape dynamics can be gained, leveraging both local knowledge and
101 scientific analysis (Agrawal, 1995; Berkes, 2012; Ogunbameru & Muller, 1996). While
102 scientists can monitor variables difficult to detect through direct observation and relate them
103 to landscape processes, their methods may be limited in understanding socio-ecological
104 dynamics, which local peoples can describe qualitatively, often offering historical insights
105 through intergenerational knowledge (Chalmers & Fabricius, 2007). Furthermore, the
106 integration of diverse knowledge systems can also serve as a reference for dialogue, ground
107 truthing, and cross-validation (Robbins, 2003).

108 The highlands of southeast Angola, which are one of the most isolated and remote areas of
109 Africa, host some of the continent's best-preserved dry forests and miombo woodlands. The
110 isolation of this region as a consequence of the Angolan civil war, has been important to
111 maintain much of the region's ecosystems. This area plays a crucial role in sustaining the
112 water systems of south-central Africa, serving as sources and tributaries for key rivers that
113 support downstream biodiversity and communities, including the Upper Zambezi (feeding
114 Victoria Falls) and the Cuando and Cubango (feeding the Okavango Delta in Botswana),
115 among others. The region is home to communities whose livelihoods depend on natural
116 resources, particularly water bodies and wooded areas. Notably, the absence of both the state
117 and markets shapes a unique context for land management and socio-ecological dynamics.
118 Given its ecological significance and the ongoing dependence of local communities on these
119 resources, this area is a candidate for conservation interventions. However, the role and
120 perceptions of local communities in this ecosystem remain largely unexplored.

121

122 This study examines vegetation classification in the highlands of Southeast Angola,
123 comparing participatory methods with remote sensing approaches to highlight the value of
124 local knowledge in the process of mapping vegetation. Specifically, we address three research
125 questions: 1) What are the locally perceived vegetation types? 2) How do maps of local land
126 classifications compare with maps relying solely on remote sensing information? 3) What are
127 the uses of each vegetation type for local livelihoods, and are these uses unique to each
128 vegetation type?
129

130 2. Methods

131

132 2.1 Study area

133

134 This study was conducted in the highlands of southeast Angola. Field work was centered
135 around five communities within the region, and maps were developed for the entire highland
136 region (Fig. 1, red polygon). The communities belong to *Luchaze* and *Tchokwé* ethnic and
137 linguistic groups. Population density is among the lowest in the country, at 0.3 persons/km²
138 (Instituto Nacional de Estatística Angola, 2014). According to Angolan Law (Lei de Terras,
139 2004), land is owned by the State, but recognizes the rights of rural communities, including
140 those rooted in customary use. Traditionally, land is inherited through kinship ties and
141 managed collectively by communities (which are often composed of interrelated families),
142 with key landscape management activities centered on agriculture and burning. Communities
143 depend on agriculture, honey production, hunting, and collection of wood and non-timber
144 forest products for subsistence and income generation. In terms of livelihoods, men typically
145 lead hunting activities, honey production, construction, and medicinal plant collection, while
146 women are primarily responsible for firewood collection and gathering wild foods. Both
147 genders engage in agricultural practices.
148

149 The study area has a topography of low, rolling hills, with woodlands and forests at higher
150 elevations and rivers and grasslands at lower elevations (Fig. 1). Previous land classifications
151 of the area display various vegetation classes including peatlands, miombo woodlands, and
152 grasslands (Burgess et al., 2004; Lourenco et al., 2023; White, 1983; Andrews et al., 2024).
153

154 Climate is seasonal with high temperatures and wet conditions during the summer and low
155 temperatures and dry conditions during the winter. The rainy season extends from mid-
156 October to the end of April, and the dry season starts in May and lasts until mid- October.
157 Mean daily temperature ranges from 10°C to 28°C (United States Geological Survey, 2020)
158 and rainfall in the area averages 1030mm ± 100mm (mean ± SD) per year (Funk et al., 2015).
159 Elevation ranges from 1220 to 1580 masl (Conservation Science Partners, 2024). The entire
160 study area that was mapped comprises 184,220 km². Most of the highlands of the southeast
161 are located within the Moxico province, with a small portion extending into the provinces of
162 Bié and Cuando Cubango. We developed our ground-based work in the province of Moxico.
163

164
 165 **Fig. 1.** Study area in southeast Angola and communities where work was undertaken. Data sources:
 166 Google Earth. Map produced with ArcGIS Pro v.3.1.3.

167
 168 **2.2. Data collection**

169 Fieldwork took place from November 2021 to June 2023, over a total of six months.
 170 Fieldwork aimed to identify the major vegetation types according to local perceptions
 171 (current personal interpretations of the landscape) and knowledge (collective understanding,
 172 practices and beliefs passed on through generations), how these are used, and where they
 173 occur. A range of field methods were employed, including participatory mapping, transect
 174 walks, rapid surveys, and the collection of geo-referenced data points in different vegetation
 175 types. All participants provided informed consent prior to their involvement in this study.

176 Participatory mapping combined with discussion groups were conducted in the villages of
 177 Sayoswa, Tempué, Sassungu, Samununga, and Sete (Fig. 1), to identify locally perceived
 178 vegetation types, their spatial distribution, and their significance for local livelihoods.
 179 Discussions were facilitated with the support of a local translator using semi-structured
 180 interviews, encouraging participants to produce maps reflecting their vegetation
 181 classifications. Groups were stratified by gender and further divided by age. In total, 20
 182 discussion groups were conducted, comprising twelve male-only and eight female-only
 183 sessions. Eight groups were of less than 25 years old, seven groups were of ages between 25
 184 and 50 and four groups were of ages older than 50 years old. Participants had experience in

185 various subsistence activities, since individuals typically engage in multiple activities rather
186 than specializing in a single one.

187 To complement these discussions and further explore how local communities classify and use
188 vegetation types, transect walks were carried out with 17 key informants (locals who hold
189 well-developed knowledge around the uses and characteristics of the landscape). In most
190 cases, informants were selected by *sobas*, the local traditional authority, whilst other times
191 they were suggested by members of the community. We carried out ten walks with
192 individuals younger than 25 years old, and 7 walks with individuals between 25 and 50 years
193 old, totaling 15 men and 2 women. These walks, lasting between two to four hours, extended
194 in multiple directions from each village. Upon encountering a new vegetation type, semi-
195 structured interviews were conducted to document distinguishing characteristics, common
196 tree species, resource use, and local management practices. At each stop, geographic
197 coordinates were recorded (with a Garmin GPSmap 62) to serve in supervised classification
198 mapping.

199 A total of 114 individual, rapid closed-end surveys were carried out using a stratified random
200 sampling approach, focused on inhabitants of the village that were old enough to
201 independently perform activities in the landscape. 55% of our interviewees were men and
202 45% women, while 20% were youth, 40% middle aged and 20% elder (for more detailed
203 demographics of the respondents see supplementary materials, Online resource 1).
204 Participants were asked to identify locations where they carried out resource-based activities
205 using a digital map on a tablet. For each location, they also provided qualitative information
206 on vegetation uses, resources, tree species, animal presence, perceived changes over time,
207 and management practices. Interviews lasted between 20 to 30 minutes, and data collection
208 continued across additional individuals until saturation was reached. Surveys were conducted
209 using ArcGIS Field Maps v24.1.1 and results were recorded on an iPad.

210 To support the classification of vegetation types, ground-based observations were collected
211 throughout the study area. Using a handheld GPS (Garmin GPSmap 62), a total of 342
212 georeferenced vegetation records were gathered during transect walks or while moving
213 between villages (either by foot or by car), always having a local travelling with us to identify
214 types of vegetation. The points collected for each type varied across vegetation formations as
215 the data collection was opportunistic. The number of points included 81 for savannas, 76 for
216 shrublands, 57 for dense woodlands, and 115 for open woodlands. Grasslands and rivers were
217 identified through Google Earth imagery and later verified through field observations.

218 2.3 Data analyses

219

220 *RQ1. What are the locally perceived vegetation types?*

221 **To address RQ1** we employed a data triangulation approach, leveraging information from
222 participatory mapping, transect walks and surveys, to identify the main vegetation types, and
223 to confirm or contrast responses whilst providing depth to the information collected
224 (Nemarundwe & Richards, 2002; Nightingale, 2016). We performed the triangulation

225 separately for each community, which allowed us to identify similarities and differences both
226 among respondents and across villages, and to formulate follow-up questions to confirm or
227 contrast our findings. We also analyzed responses by gender, to assess any gender-based
228 differences. For the results, we synthesized the data from all villages to provide overall
229 insights into landscape dynamics of the region. We cleaned and analyzed qualitative data
230 using *Nvivo* v.12 software (QSR International, 2018).

231

232 To identify the main vegetation types from the field data, we used a thematic inductive
233 coding approach (i.e., themes were established after starting the data collection rather than
234 beforehand, and each theme represented a vegetation type). Furthermore, attributes were
235 assigned to each theme, including a) general descriptions, b) activities/uses, c) animal species
236 found, d) tree species found, e) management and intensity of use, and f) perceived importance
237 for subsistence.

238

239 *RQ2. How do local land classifications compare with remote sensing-only classifications?*

240 **To address RQ2**, we created two types of maps, one with only the inputs from satellite-
241 derived data (an unsupervised classification), and one using the same satellite data, but with
242 additional ground-based observations of vegetation type derived from the local classification
243 (a supervised classification).

244 For optical data, the classifications used 20 m resolution imagery from Sentinel-2 dataset
245 (bands B2, B3, B4, B8, B11, B12; ESA, 2023). The imagery acquired was from the dry
246 season of 2022 (May to October) when cloud cover was lowest (30% cloud cover threshold).
247 The dry season also offers greater visual contrast among vegetation types, enhancing
248 distinctions between denser, evergreen woodlands and deciduous woodlands. We used a
249 median composite with a total of 50 images. In addition to Sentinel satellite imagery, we used
250 the following three data layers:

- 251 - *Fire layer*: We used MODIS Burned Area data (MODIS/061/MCD64A1; Giglio et
252 al., 2021) which is a monthly product with a resolution of 500 meters. We identified
253 pixels burned in each image within the study area (the product classifies a pixel as
254 fully burned, even if only a portion was affected by fire). We then assigned binary
255 values; 1 to years that had burned pixels and 0 to years that had unburned pixels. We
256 then summed the number of years a pixel burned from 2000 to 2022.
- 257 - *Vegetation seasonality*: We used the Normalized Difference of Vegetation Index
258 (NDVI) as a proxy for differences in vegetation dynamics and tree density (Mitchard
259 & Flintrop, 2013; Wells et al., 2025) from the Sentinel-2 dataset
260 (COPERNICUS/S2_SR_HARMONIZED; European Space Agency, 2023).
- 261 - *Topographic position index*: We used the Shuttle Radar Topographic Mission
262 (SRTM) dataset to add a precomputed index of the relative topographic position of
263 each pixel (TPI) (CSP/ERGo/1_0/Global/ SRTM_Mtpi; Conservation Science
264 Partners, 2024) within the study area. TPI is a relative measure of the position of a
265 specific point in relation to the position of its surroundings, and can be useful for

266 indicating relative position on local catenal sequences (see code for the spatial
267 analysis in in the supplementary materials, Online Resource 2).

268

269 These three variables were included in both mapping approaches because African vegetation
270 ecology literature often suggests that fire, tree density, and topography are key determinants
271 of vegetation patterns (White, 1983; Chidumayo, 1997; Campbell, 1996). Locals also raised
272 these factors as important in determining vegetation types in focal discussion groups.

273

274 To create the unsupervised maps, we used a *K-means* clustering approach as this does not
275 require prior knowledge of the classes. In order to compare both approaches, we set the
276 number of classes in the unsupervised map to be the same as documented during our
277 fieldwork on the ground (six classes; five land classes plus rivers). For the supervised
278 classification, we used a random forest model with the same data layers used for the
279 unsupervised classification, along with ground-based geo-referenced observations of
280 vegetation types, obtained during fieldwork. We used 70% of the data points for training and
281 30% of the points for validation, and generated a confusion matrix, which can be found in the
282 supplementary materials, Online resource 3.

283

284 To visually compare the supervised and unsupervised classifications, we created a Sankey
285 diagram. Unsupervised classes were identified and colored as the class that had the highest
286 correspondence to the classes in the supervised classification. New classes/colors in the
287 unsupervised classification were added if a class did not clearly correspond to any class in the
288 supervised classification. Second, we conducted ANOVA tests to compare NDVI, TPI, and
289 fire count across classes in both classification schemes. To do this, we generated 100 random
290 points per vegetation type and extracted the corresponding values.

291 We used Google Earth Engine for spatial analyses and the function *Extract values to points*
292 from *ArcGIS Pro v.3.1.3*. We also used the R Statistical Environment *RStudio v.4.3.2* (R Core
293 Team, 2019) for statistical analyses, including *Raster package v.3.6-26* (Hijmans, 2023).

294

295 *RQ3. What are the uses of each vegetation type for local livelihoods and are these uses*
296 *unique to each vegetation type?*

297

298 **To address RQ3**, we first identified the uses of each vegetation type from the rapid surveys,
299 compiling a list of all reported uses. These lists were then triangulated with data from
300 participatory mapping and transect walks. We used the supervised map generated in RQ2 to
301 spatially represent the number of livelihood activities performed across different vegetation
302 types. We ranked the vegetation types from the ones that had the highest number of different
303 uses to the ones that had the fewest.

304

305 3. Results

306

307 3.1. Main vegetation types based on local perception

308

309 *Qualitative descriptions of vegetation types according to local perceptions*

310 Locals identify seven vegetation types in the area: five wooded types and two grassland
311 types. We assigned English names to each of them, which correspond to names used in
312 Southern African woodland literature (e.g., Campbell, 1996; Chidumayo, 1997). The
313 classification and descriptions are based on local ecological knowledge (Table 1).

Table 1. Descriptions of vegetation types in southeast Angola, gathered through participatory methods that leverage local knowledge

Local Name	Correspondence with English names	Structure	Dominating Tree Species	Main Activities	Animals	Management	Notes	
Lihumbu	Dense woodland	High stem density with diverse tree sizes, dominated by small-diameter stems. Moss covers soils, with few grasses, and abundant shrubs	<i>Cryptosepalum exfoliatum</i> subsp. <i>pseudotaxus</i> , <i>Burkea africana</i> , <i>Diospyros mespiliformis</i> subsp. <i>brevicalyx</i> , <i>Brachystegia bakeriana</i> , <i>B. spiciformis</i> , <i>Landolphia camptoloba</i>	Agriculture, collection of wild foods and construction materials, hunting, honey production	Gazelle, guineafowl, wild pigs, monkeys	Rarely burns; edges may burn from nearby agricultural fires. Trees mainly cut for agriculture and construction	Essential for agriculture; crops include corn, pearl millet, cassava, and beans	
Nkangala	Miombo woodland	Open with tall, thick trees	<i>Julbernardia paniculata</i> , <i>Brachystegia spiciformis</i> , <i>Erythrophleum africanum</i> , <i>Parinari curatellifolia</i> , <i>Guibourtia coleosperma</i>	Agriculture (best place for cassava), honey production, hunting, wild foods collection	Sable antelope, wild pigs, deer, monkeys, lions	Patchy burning every 2-3 years; fire used to clear land, improve visibility, and for honey harvesting	Some patches experience animal scarcity. Larger trees are fire-resistant. Vegetation gets denser further from rivers	
Chitete	Shrubland	Abundant shrubs with few large trees; variable grass cover	<i>Brachystegia bakeriana</i> (mainly as a shrub), <i>Monotes</i> spp., <i>Erythrophleum africanum</i> , <i>Burkea africana</i> , <i>Guibourtia coleosperma</i> , <i>Julbernardia paniculata</i> , <i>Brachystegia longifolia</i>	Firewood collection, medicine and wild foods collection	Deer, rodents, wild pigs	Burned to clear understorey, stimulate leaf growth, and improve safety (by deterring snakes)	Firewood scarcity reported, leading to increased travel distances for collection	
Chana	Open savanna	Grass-dominated understorey with scattered small trees and shrubs	<i>Burkea africana</i> (in savannas by the river), <i>Erythrophleum africanum</i> , <i>Pterocarpus angolensis</i> , <i>Terminalia brachystemma</i> , <i>Strychnos</i> spp., <i>Monotes</i> spp., <i>Diplorhynchus condylocarpon</i>	Wild foods, medicine, and grass collection, hunting	Wild pigs, hares, rabbits, rodents	Mostly burned early in the dry season (often annually) to deter snakes, stimulate grass, underground trees and herbaceous growth. Leaf regrowth helps attract animals for hunting	Important for wild honey production (from <i>Cryptosepalum maraviense</i> , underground trees) and construction materials from termite mounds; usually lower stem density near rivers and higher at greater elevations	

Chipapa	Open woodland	Open wooded areas; defined as a mix of miombo and savanna and as former dense woodland altered by fire	<i>Hymenocardia acida</i> , <i>Dialium englerianum</i> , <i>Burkea africana</i> , <i>Guibourtia coleosperma</i> , <i>Diplorhynchus condylocarpon</i> , <i>Erythrophleum africanum</i> , <i>Monotes spp.</i>	Wild foods and medicine collection, construction materials, hunting, beekeeping	Deer, wild pigs	Burned heavily, often annually due to fires from nearby crop fields	Bracken common in the understorey; not greatly valued or used for any livelihood activity	
Chizansa	Riverine grassland	No trees, dominated by grasses, mainly <i>Loudetia spp.</i>	-	Soils used for growing vegetables. Grass used for construction materials (ceilings, walls, brooms)	-	Burned either accidentally by spill-over fires or for soil preparation for vegetable gardens	Remains waterlogged year-round	
Chimpoka	Upland grassland	Dominated by grasses and geoxylic suffrutices	-	Grass used for construction materials (ceilings, walls, brooms)	-	Burned accidentally by spill-over fires	Remains wet only during the rainy season	

3.2. Comparison between supervised and unsupervised vegetation classification

First, it is worth clarifying that although locals differentiate between two types of open woodlands and two types of grasslands (Table 1), our mapping exercises include only four classes of woody vegetation and one type of grassland. Due to limited ground truth data, the grasslands were merged into a single class, as they are structurally similar and often occur adjacent to each other. Similarly, open woodlands were combined with miombo woodlands in the mapping process because of their reported structural similarities and because we did not have enough ground data points to map them separately.

The two methods to classify vegetation revealed important differences, with each approach showing variations in land cover across different catenal positions. In our study, unsupervised maps do not differentiate dense woodlands from open woodlands (Fig. 2 and 3). Furthermore, while 99% of dense woodlands from the supervised map fall within class 0 of the unsupervised map, they only make up 35% of class 0. Class 0 also contains 61% of the open woodlands from the supervised map.

Fig. 2. A) Unsupervised land cover classification of the region with six classes (to match the five vegetation types described by locals and mapped in the supervised classification, plus rivers). B) Supervised classification using data points collected in the field based on local classifications of the vegetation, with an 88% validation accuracy. Classifications used Sentinel-2 data (European Space

Agency, 2023), fire (fire count; MODIS; Giglio et al., 2021) and topography data (Conservation Science Partners, 2024). Unsupervised classes were assigned colors based on the supervised class with the highest correspondence. New colors were added when an unsupervised class corresponded to multiple supervised classes or when the match is otherwise unclear. Maps were produced with ArcGIS Pro v.3.1.3.

Fig. 3. Insets from selected locations in the supervised and unsupervised classifications, where a) the supervised classification distinguishes dense woodlands from open woodlands (light green and dark green) as compared to b) the unsupervised classification and, c) the supervised classification gives fewer vegetation classes in savannas and shrublands than d) the unsupervised classification.

Notably, every vegetation type from the supervised classification contributed to class 0, including approximately 50% of savannas and grasslands and 25% of shrublands (Fig. 4). Additionally, some shrubland and savanna areas were distributed across all five classes in the unsupervised classification, highlighting variability and overlap between categories.

Fig. 4. Sankey diagram (produced in RStudio) comparing the unsupervised classification (on the left side) to the supervised classification (on the right side). The numbers on the left represent the classes derived from the unsupervised classification, while the categories on the right correspond to the vegetation types identified in the supervised classification. The width of the flows connecting the two sides indicates the proportion of area within each unsupervised class that corresponds to a specific vegetation type. The colors used are the same as in Fig. 2.

To further assess the differences among mapping approaches, we looked at the differences in fire count, vegetation patterns (assessed through NDVI) and topographic position index (TPI) of each class on both maps. For fire count we found significantly different counts among each class for both unsupervised ($F_{4,345} = 24.8, p < 2e^{-16}$) and supervised classification ($F_{4,344} = 93.1, p < 2e^{-16}$). For NDVI, also both the classes in the unsupervised map ($F_{4,345} = 259.7, p < 2e^{-16}$) and supervised classes ($F_{4,344} = 130, p < 2e^{-16}$) were significantly different. As for TPI, significant differences were also shown in both the unsupervised ($F_{4,345} = 2.9, p=0.2$) and supervised classifications ($F_{4,344} = 25.7, p < 2e^{-16}$). Notably, the F statistic is higher for the supervised classification in relation to the unsupervised map, for both the fire count and the TPI, suggesting a higher variation among classes for these two variables in the supervised classification. Boxplots of differences among fire count, NDVI and TPI can be found in the supplementary materials, Online Resource 4.

3.3. Uses of the vegetation

Eight key uses of the different vegetation types were identified: (i) agriculture, (ii) honey production, (iii) hunting, (iv) wild food collection, (v) firewood collection, (vi) wood harvesting for construction, tools, and artifacts, (vii) grass collection for practical uses, and (viii) medicinal plant collection (Table 2). The results also show that different vegetation types are used for different purposes across the region. However, vegetation types in this region serve for multiple activities and provide multiple products and services. We found that

miombo woodlands are used for all activities (eight in total, Fig. 5) followed by dense woodlands (seven activities). Savannas, shrublands and open woodlands can be used for up to six activities and grasslands for two activities. Honey collection, hunting, wild food gathering, wood harvesting for construction and tools, firewood collection, medicinal plant use, and grass collection can be performed in all vegetation types.

Table 2. Uses of each vegetation cover and total uses for each.

Vegetation types	Agriculture	Honey	Hunting	Wild food	Wood (construction, artefacts, tools)	Firewood	Medicines	Grass collection	Total uses
Miombo woodland	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	8
Dense woodland	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	7
Open woodland	no	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	6
Shrubland	no	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	6
Savanna	no	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	6
Grassland	yes	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes	2

Fig. 5. Map showing vegetation types colored by the number of recorded uses, from the most uses (miombo woodlands) to the least (grasslands). Map produced with ArcGIS Pro v.3.1.3.

4. Discussion

Our study highlights consequential differences between maps generated using standard, pure remote sensing approaches versus those that incorporate ground-based field work and consultation with local communities. Unsupervised maps struggled to distinguish dense woodlands from open woodlands, and suggested greater land cover diversity in open lowland

areas. The unsupervised classification mixed vegetation types that local people recognize, particularly in the largest unsupervised class, which encompassed portions of five supervised classes. This overlap underscores challenges in differentiating vegetation types using remote methods, likely due to shared spectral or structural characteristics among locally recognized vegetation types, which we consider to be distinct ecosystems, ecologically and culturally. Furthermore, the incorporation of topographic position index and fire count into this study helped understand the differences among vegetation types. For instance, dense woodlands were characterized by the lowest fire frequency, whilst savannas experienced the highest, reflecting their ecological and functional differences. Lastly, vegetation classes demonstrated multifunctionality (Otte et al., 2007; Stürck & Verburg, 2017), with each vegetation type supporting from two to eight livelihood and income generating activities. The following discussion emphasizes the contributions of participatory methods to remote sensing-based landscape classification, the importance of recognizing local land uses and the implications of participatory approaches for the understanding and managing of landscapes.

4.1 Contributions of participatory methods to remote sensing approaches for the classification of vegetation

Our findings suggest that while remote sensing (RS) approaches provide valuable large-scale insights into land characteristics, the inherent uncertainties with RS approaches, such as discrepancies with ground reference data (Foody, 2002) and classification errors (Olofsson et al., 2013), highlight the need to integrate ground data to produce refined maps that reflect local realities. For instance, in this study, dense and open woodlands were frequently classified under the same class when using satellite data only. As revealed by local knowledge, these two vegetation covers have different uses and fire regimes, for example, some patches of dense woodlands have only burned one to two times in the last 23 years, while open woodlands can burn up to eight times more. Merging open and dense woodlands in the same vegetation type can therefore result in homogenized management approaches that might threaten individual ecosystems.

Integrating local knowledge with satellite data also provides a more nuanced understanding of vegetation differences at the local level, highlighting key landscape functions, such as the provision of non-timber forest products (e.g., mushrooms, grasses, and medicinal plants). This integration can enhance scientific land classification and bring visibility to local land users. In this context, we argue that participatory mapping serves as a means to legitimize local knowledge, recognizing it as equally valid as conventional scientific methods. Our findings then suggest that viewing landscapes as socio-ecological systems (Ostrom, 2009), rather than purely ecological ones (Lambin et al., 2006), leads to a more comprehensive understanding of landscape dynamics.

4.2 Vegetation use and cover

Our results reveal that most livelihood activities span across multiple vegetation classes, highlighting the multifunctionality of the landscape, a pattern observed in other African contexts (Roth, 2009; Cumming & Lynam, 1997). Having alternative places for livelihood activities provides a safety net for local people and translates into less pressure on only one type of vegetation. The value of this landscape lies not just in specific vegetation types, but in the diversity of vegetation and resources they offer, a diversity that is important from both an ecological and a social perspective.

Notably, we found that locals perceive vegetation type and its uses as inherently interconnected, rather than as distinct aspects. From a socio-ecological perspective, vegetation classification and its practical uses are often inseparable, reflecting an integrated understanding of the landscape (Robbins & Maddock, 2000). In this context, a mixed methods approach proved crucial for unravelling these complexities.

Moreover, participatory approaches can help uncover the motivations behind resource use, revealing that the choice of vegetation type might be influenced by factors beyond resource availability, such as collection costs (e.g., distance) or social dynamics (e.g., gender and time constraints) (Lynam et al., 2004). Gender, along with seasonality and the quality and quantity of natural resources, has been recognized as a key factor in the spatial organization of productive activities in rural landscapes (Roth, 2009; Pritchard et al., 2019). In our study site, women primarily focused their activities (and thus the discussions) in shrublands near villages, for firewood collection, and on woodlands, for agriculture. Men, whose activities, e.g., hunting, fishing, and honey harvesting, often take them further, provided detailed descriptions of more distant locations. These observations highlight the importance of understanding such dynamics in the broader context of landscape use.

4.3 Potential implications for different mapping approaches

Mapping methods can have significant implications for land users, especially when maps inform decisions about landscape management. For example, areas with high forest cover, often prioritized in conservation efforts (see Blackman, 2013) for their role in carbon sequestration, soil preservation, and wildlife habitat, may also be essential to local livelihoods (Lynam et al., 2004). In southeast Angola, dense woodlands are vital to local communities, providing essential resources for their livelihoods and restricting its use risks disrupting local livelihoods. Importantly, while these woodlands hold potential for carbon sequestration, current patterns of local use do not appear to significantly diminish their ability to store carbon. This suggests that, with proper management, local use and conservation can coexist without major trade-offs in carbon storage potential. Additionally, vegetation types such as savannas, often considered less valuable in ecological functions, are crucial to rural economies, providing valuable non-timber resources (Pritchard et al., 2019).

Given the remoteness and well-preserved condition of the highlands in southeast Angola, conservation interventions are likely, and here we argue, they should be grounded in a socio-ecological perspective that bridges scientific analysis with local perspectives. For any land

intervention, it is crucial to question assumptions about what constitutes an ‘ideal’ landscape and whose values define it (Pritchard et al., 2021; Wyborn and Evans, 2021). Participatory methods can represent a vehicle to identify what local users envision for their landscape, which can ultimately enhance the effectiveness and acceptance of conservation initiatives. Ultimately, interventions that align with local preferences, promote sustainable resource use, and encourage inclusive management are more likely to empower local communities, supporting cultural and livelihood benefits and leading to positive conservation and social outcomes (Löfqvist et al., 2023; Oldekop et al., 2016; Schleicher et al., 2019).

4.4 Limitations: to map or not to map?

As for any research approach, mapping does not always do justice to local perceptions, knowledge and realities, since some human dimensions cannot be easily mapped (Wyborn & Evans, 2021). Maps are inherently selective, offering a particular way of looking at the world, and often not displaying all there is to know about any given place (Malavasi, 2020). For instance, how many and which types of vegetation exist in a landscape is arbitrary, as it relates to the purpose of the classification. In our mapping process we questioned if our representations of the landscape aligned with local perceptions since we encountered challenges in the process of translating qualitative data into maps. We also struggled to draw boundaries between vegetation types, as local classification systems often recognize fluid and overlapping categories (McCall & Dunn, 2012). This highlights the challenge of fitting ecological complexity into rigid classification frameworks.

Lastly, we found challenges in portraying variability within vegetation types expressed by individual or collective experiences, and the descriptions of the vegetation types in this study are likely a simplification of the diversity of local perceptions and knowledges. For instance, when comparing participatory maps produced by different groups from the same village as well as among groups in different villages, maps varied, possibly a result of personal experiences, gender, and occupation, among other factors. This emphasizes that local knowledge is not “fixed”, as there might be contrasting views not only between empirical and scientific knowledge but also between various local knowledges (Andolina et al., 2009; Gilmore & Young, 2012).

5 Conclusion

Our study demonstrates that local communities in southeast Angola recognize distinct vegetation types beyond what is typically captured through remote sensing approaches, identifying five woodland types in addition to grasslands and rivers. These classifications diverge from remote sensing-only approaches, which struggled to distinguish key ecological differences, particularly between dense and open woodlands. Moreover, vegetation types are not just ecological categories for local communities; they are deeply tied to their livelihoods. Each vegetation type supports multiple uses, ranging from agriculture and honey production to firewood collection and non-timber forest products, demonstrating their multifunctionality.

By integrating participatory methods with remote sensing, we bridge the gap between technical classifications and the lived realities of land use, ensuring that both social and ecological dimensions of landscapes are recognized. This approach challenges conservation and management strategies that rely solely on remote sensing, which can produce homogenized policies misaligned with local priorities. Recognizing local knowledge in mapping and land-use planning fosters more just and effective conservation efforts while reinforcing the role of local communities as active stewards of their landscapes. This is relevant as these communities are often key agents in sustaining vegetation diversity and ecosystem health to ensure ecosystems continue meeting their needs (Pratzer et al., 2023), highlighting the necessity of locally led governance in natural resource management (Friedman et al., 2022).

Declarations

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Ethics Approval

This study was conducted in accordance with the UK Research Integrity Office's Code of Practice for Research and was approved by the Research Ethics and Integrity Committee of the School of Geosciences at the University of Edinburgh.

Consent to Participate

All participants provided informed consent prior to their involvement in the study.

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